

THE CONSTRUCTION OF THE BIG FERGHANA CANAL – THE REAL COURAGEOUS EXAMPLE OF UZBEK PEOPLE

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Abstract: In this article, the history of the construction of the Great Fergana Canal is researched on the basis of unique archival documents.

Key words: history, Ferghana canal, hashar, water, improvement.

According to valuable archive documents

Figure 1. The construction process of the Big Fergana Canal

This year marks the 84th anniversary of the construction of the Big Ferghana Canal, which united the Uzbek people towards a common goal, reflected examples of true heroism, and became a symbol of unity, harmony, and self-sacrifice. It's done.

The history of the Big Fergana Canal, which made a big difference in improving the living standards of the peoples of Central Asia, is interesting and certainly surprising for all of us. The reason for this is that the soil was excavated mainly by hand, and it was completed and it is the largest hydrotechnical structure built in the Fergana Valley.

It is even more important that it was started in the hot summer season of 1939 and was completed in a short period of time, in 45 days (1).

According to the documents related to the construction of the Big Fergana Canal kept by the state archive of Fergana region, the decision No. 896 of the Council of People's

Commissars of the Uzbek SSR dated June 3-6, 1939 on "Construction of the Big Fergana Canal" was adopted. (Fund-1124, List-2, Collection-3)

Figure 2. Resolution №896

Figure 3. Resolution №896

Figure 4. Resolution №896

Figure 5. Resolution №896

Also, in this decision, the construction schemes were approved, and Mirzayev Teshavoy was approved as the construction manager.

Mirzayev Teshavoy

Hoes, stretchers and shovels were the main tools of the builders. Builders did not have modern vehicles, so about 12,000 carts and 7,000 four-wheeled carts were used to transport soil and bring building materials.

The construction process of the Big Fergana Canal

More than 510,000 cubic meters of soil were removed from the canal in the first days of work on the canal. According to information, 180,000 workers and farmers and 3,000 engineers and technicians participated in the national strike.

Another noteworthy point is that during the excavation of the 270-kilometer long canal, 17 mln. m3 of soil was mined, of which only 1.7 mln. m3 of soil (10 percent of the total) was excavated using machinery. This is a proof that the Uzbek people are a

hardworking people, organized towards the common goals of improving the nation's lifestyle.

In addition, during this construction process, various methods were used for the cultural release of insects. Throughout the construction campaign centers, radio centers, libraries, mass-circulation newspapers as well

as publicists informed the builders about the results, pace and quality of daily work - who was ahead and who was lagging behind.

Also, a number of national heroes who showed sacrifice during the construction of this canal were discovered. Another document in fund 1124 in the archive contains a list of citizens who took a special place in the construction, showed courage

with their hard work, and participated in the digging of the canal.

Also, a number of national heroes who showed sacrifice during the construction of this canal were discovered. In the documents of the "Working Deputies Executive Committee of Fergana Region" belonging to Fund 1124 in the State Archives of Fergana Region (Fund-1124, List-2, Gathering-43), he had a special place in the construction, his there is a name-by-name list of citizens who participated in the digging of the canal, showing courage with their hard work.

Region (Fund-1124, List-2, Gathering-43), he had a special place in the construction, his there is a name-by-name list of citizens who participated in the digging of the canal, showing courage with their hard work.

The canal was named "Katta Fergana Canal named after Usman Yusupov" in honor of Usman Yusupov, who was the head of the government of Uzbekistan during the construction of this water facility and was involved in these works, and also in the part of the canal flowing through Rishton district bust mounted.

Usmon Yusupov
Those who took part in the construction of the Big Ferghana Canal, who were able to demonstrate the values that the construction of the canal unites our people towards one goal, and play an important role in the further

formation of good ideas such as kindness and organization among them, have now matured. is truly an example of true courage for the younger generation.

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